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D4.3: Final prototype of the ICT-based DAP

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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Deadline	Done by
1	DAP User Interface validated (Milestone MS20)	31/7/2022	19/09/2022
2	Submission of Draft Deliverable to reviewers	22/7/2022	08/12/2022
3	Uploading and submission of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal	31/7/2022	19/12/2022

Executive summary

This report is the accompanying document for Deliverable 4.3 (type: demonstrator), namely the “Final prototype of the ICT based Decision Analytic Platform (DAP)”. The main objective of Project Ô is to demonstrate innovative approaches and technologies to support the circular economy, addressing the technical, economic, environmental, and social aspects to redefine water value chains. Project Ô Work Package 4 targets designing, developing, and testing an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policymakers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management strategies and water reuse technologies.

The ICT based DAP is a platform targeting mainly water regulators, relying on a multi-objective decision-making approach to allow the analysis of traditionally incommensurable and conflicting objectives and to explore their trade-offs.

The final DAP Prototype has been populated for demo-site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP) system, in Italy, with data and simulation presented in Deliverable D4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions) and Deliverable D4.4 (Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis). It is now hosted on the Politecnico di Milano server infrastructure and available at the following Url: <https://xake.deib.polimi.it:8080/dap>.

The DAP prototype relies on a stack of open-source software mixing mature software solutions and custom modules developed ad-hoc: links to code repositories of the latest are provided, to ensure re-usability and future development of this product.

Table of Contents

Deliverable Review and Approval.....	2
Deliverable Development and Review Process.....	2
Executive summary.....	3
1 Introduction.....	5
2 Platform overview.....	7
2.1 User interface Functionalities.....	7
2.2 Platform architecture.....	13
3 DAP Demonstrator.....	15
4 DAP User Feedback Report.....	16
4.1 Introduction.....	16
4.2 Methods.....	16
4.3 Results: Overall.....	16
4.4 Results: Demonstration feedback.....	19
4.5 Results: User Perceptions & Experiences.....	21
4.6 User survey conclusion.....	25
Appendix I – User Testing Feedback Questionnaire.....	26

1 Introduction

This document is the deliverable D4.3 - *Final prototype of the ICT based DAP (demonstrator)*, which is part of Work Package (WP) 4 activities undertaken in task T4.3 *ICT-based decision-analytic platform*.

The main objective of Project Ô is to demonstrate innovative approaches and technologies to support an integrated and symbiotic use and re-use of water by contributing to the transition to a circular economy, addressing the technical, economic, environmental, and social aspects, to redefine some water value chains. New water treatment technologies developed by WP2 (see Figure 2) are different in scope, but all are characterized by their relatively high energy efficiency and low cost. On the one hand, this requires a modular approach and a novel control unit based on new smart sensors; on the other information and decision-making, support is needed for all stakeholders involved in the planning and management of water resources.

Project Ô provides this support through different software tools:

- a Decision Analytics Platform (DAP, from WP4), targeting mainly water regulators, relying on a multi-objective decision-making approach to allow the analysis of traditionally incommensurable and conflicting objectives and to exploring their trade-offs;
- a demonstrative Technology Selection Toolbox (from WP7), allowing to select of the best technology to match water requirements (in terms of quantity and quality) with local, “alternative” water availability;
- a User Collaborative Platform (UCP, from WP7), mainly business-facing, to promote a symbiotic exchange of water volumes over a defined territory to improve the circularity of resources between different partners involved in the water treatment value chains.

Figura 1: ProjectÔ Work packages interdependencies

The Decision Analytic Platform is the object of the present document, while the Technology Selection Toolbox has been developed in the deliverable D7.1, and the third tool of the list, the UCP, has been described and published in the deliverables D7.2 and D7.3, respectively. Figure 2 shows the link between all Project Ô WPs: WP4 acts as collector for performance data of the technologies developed in other WPs and Stakeholders' needs in term of decisions support for planning and management.

The DAP platform aims to support the planning and decision-making process, to evaluate different options for water reuse, considering not only traditional sources of water by restoring polluted wells as auxiliary sources for drinking water distribution networks, or by exploiting refined water from wastewater treatment plants to irrigate suitable crops. Considering these options will enable platform users to explore the trade-offs between treatment costs, water shortages' impact on different users, and the overall system resilience during plausible future emergencies (e.g. prolonged droughts, increasing demands, events of reduction supply system capacity, etc...).

The final DAP prototype demonstrator is focused on the Apulian demo site (in Italy), due to its complexity and spatial extension, where greater emphasis is placed on the decision-making component of medium-term planning. Data and simulation published in the platform have been documented in Deliverable D4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions) and Deliverable D4.4 (Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis, due for month 54, corresponding to November 30, 2022).

The delivery delay of the present report is due to the fact that, while the DAP prototype interface development was completed already on September 2022 (see Milestone MS20) and has been running online since then, the results published in Report D4.4 were needed to upload the final data on the platform and finalize this report.

Section 2 of the present document will provide a complete overview of all functionalities and pages available in the DAP Prototype as well as a synthetic description of its architecture. Section 3 provides links to the demonstrator and the software repositories. Finally, Section 4 gives insights into user feedback collected after the demonstration events.

2 Platform overview

2.1 User interface Functionalities

The DAP ICT interface landing page, presented in Figure 2, is the starting point for users and it provides the following functionalities:

- top bar menu with links to navigate in the page content and to login page;
- DAP concept presentation;
- main pages and functionalities screenshots and descriptions;
- contact form;
- links to Project Ô website and social media channels;

Figura 2: DAP Prototype landing page

Once logged in, the user is directed to the Water Planning Portfolios (WPP) page (Figure 3), presenting the list of portfolios is reported, together with the WPP identification code, a short sentence describing the WPP features, links to Outline and Evaluation pages for each WPP.

Figura 3: Water Planning Portfolios page

Each WPP is evaluated against one or several scenarios. Figure 4 presents the Scenarios page, where each Hydro-climatic scenario is described through the average trajectory of the main representative variables:

- daily temperature,
- daily cumulated rainfall,
- daily cumulated inflow.

More details on how these scenarios have been computed can be found in Deliverable D4.4 “Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis”.

Figura 4: Scenario page, with average daily trajectories of Temperature for scenario RCP 4.5 2050-59

Each Water Planning Portfolio is then described in detail on the Outline page (Figure 3), where different cards describe the various actions considered. Where relevant, an interactive chart or map is attached to a specific card. Figure 3, for instance, shows the chart representing the monthly water demand for irrigation considered in WPP3.

The drop-down placed on the right in the blue menu bar allows the user to dynamically switch among different portfolios, while the icons placed on the left provide a quick, contextual, link to Evaluation Chart and Evaluation Map pages, presented later on.

Figura 5: Outline page for Water Portfolio WPP3

One of the core functionalities of the DAP is the possibility to evaluate the performance of a given combination of actions (the WPP) against different future scenarios. Figure 6 shows the Evaluation chart page that allows performing this analysis by providing some predefined charts where four main indicators are shown, as a monthly average value over ten years:

- Water irrigation deficit, divided by each one of the main reservoirs;
- Drinking Water Deficit for the entire system;
- Water Deficit For Industrial Users, existing only for Monte Cotugno reservoir;
- Drinking Water Distribution Costs for the entire system;

Additional evaluation indicators can then be added to enrich the analysis by selecting them from a bottom drop-down list.

Evaluation charts

 Assess the performance of each portfolio across different scenarios. Design indicators are already loaded on the page, but more indicators [can be added](#) and analysed.

Figura 6: Evaluation charts page for Water Portfolio WPP2

The DAP aims to provide effective tools for water resource management and planning at a large scale and, therefore, it is important to consider the geographical context of the different system components, as well as the spatial distribution of the evaluation indicators. The Evaluation Map page, as reported in Figure 7, integrates a fully featured webGIS, that allows to render and query both static layers, presenting the Apulian Aqueduct system (e.g. reservoirs, main vectors, existing wells, ..) and dynamic spatial indicators, changing the displayed values according to the combination of WPP and Scenario selected in the top blue bar drop-downs.

Figura 7: Evaluation map page for Water Portfolio WPP2 and Scenario RCP 8.5 2050-59

To complete the analysis tools, all considered combinations of WPP and scenarios can be compared on the Comparison page (Figure 8) with an interactive parallel plot chart. In the plot, each line is therefore reporting the performance against the four main indicators (the same mentioned before on the Evaluation Charts page). This tool provides many interesting features:

- each axis is scaled on its related indicator min-max range: lines position gives therefore the ranking concerning each specific indicator;
- by clicking on the axis label, several additional functionalities can be activated:
 - Dragging the axis to change its position or eventually remove it, temporarily, from the chart;
 - Reverse the axis itself;
 - Use for colouring;
 - View data distribution along that specific indicator;
- each axis can also be filtered to highlight a subset of lines and eventually single out those more interesting by iteratively adding filters on other axes;
- the dynamic table below allows the user to
 - read numbers presented in the chart;
 - search and filter among all data displayed;
 - Order table rows in ascending or descending order for each column;
 - Get quick access to WPP and scenarios description, by clicking on the related links in the table.

Comparison

Compare performances of different water portfolios against different scenarios. Filter by each axis directly on the chart to explore tradeoffs and identify the most promising solutions.

Figura 8: Comparison page, with the parallel coordinates plot and the related table

Finally a Documentation page (Figure 9) provides direct access to project reports, papers, data and software related to the DAP.

Documentation

One of the core goals of Project 0 is to demonstrate the efficacy of adopting water reuse technologies to shift towards a circular economy for long-term, sustainable water management. Project 0 Work Package 4 targets the design, development, and testing of an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management strategies and water reuse technologies. In this section you can find deliverables and publications related to WP4. Discover more on Project 0, in the project website (<https://www.eu-project-0.eu/>)

Title	Abstract	Document	Link
Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions	This deliverable D4.1 illustrates the output of the design of Multi-objective water planning portfolios for Demo site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP) system, Italy.	D4.1_portfolio.pdf	
First prototype of the ICT based DAP	First prototype of the Decision Analytics Platform (DAP), an ICT based platform to support Stakeholders and Decision Makers in exploring alternative Water Planning Portfolios, under different hydro-climatic and socio-economic scenarios, visualizing their spatially and temporally distributed effects.	D4.2_DAP_Prototype_final.pdf	
Final prototype of the ICT based DAP			
Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis			
Economic and operational model of new technologies for water efficiency and Circularity	The Task 4.2 of Project 0 aims at shedding light on the economic and operational drivers that could foster the adoption of new reuse technologies. More specifically, it models capital, operating and resource expenses and savings for the reference technologies identified based on interactions with other partners and collecting data from the extant literature, while at the same time identifying the possible policy and price regulation options and operational conditions that may be considered for the deployment of such technologies	d4.5.pdf	
Surrogate modeling for water reuse planning in complex water systems	Integrated management of water reuse technologies and coordinated operations with other water system components is fundamental to fully exploiting reuse potential. Yet, these technologies are primarily designed considering their individual efficiency more than possible synergies with traditional water management practices. In this paper, we introduce a general-purpose framework that couples physical and surrogate modelling with optimal control methods to support policy-makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management strategies and water loops. The framework is developed for the case study of the Apulia Region, Southern Italy, characterised by the presence of a complex water distribution network and multiple conflicting users across irrigation districts, industry, and urban water supply. In addition, the Apulia system shares strategic reservoirs in a drought-prone area.		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7257370

<https://xake.deib.polimi.it:8080/dap/documentation>

Figura 9: Documentation page

2.2 Platform architecture

The Decision Analytic Platform has been developed with a set of open-source software, mixing mature and well-known solutions with customized software components in order to provide features described in Section 2.1. The software architecture has been defined considering also two other targets:

- ensure synergies with the User Collaborative Platform, developed by WP7;
- provide portable and modular software solutions, oriented to commercial exploitation, coherently with the goals of the Exploitation Plan (see WP9).

A first description of the architecture and custom modules has been already provided in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.2, but since then several changes occurred in the development process: therefore this section presents the final architecture of the DAP Platform.

Figure 10 represents the final version of the stack, with the functional components in the blue-line boxes and solutions adopted for each component outside. Given the number of different services needed to support all DAP functionalities, the modular architecture already presented in Report D4.2 has been further specialized by creating a Docker container¹ for each component.

Figura 10: DAP Platform architecture

The set of containers creates a Docker stack, where all containers work in a dedicated network: this allows to refer to the single service using container names in the URLs, making the platform simpler to be managed and deployed. According to Figure 10, the stack is composed of:

¹ A Docker container image is a lightweight, standalone, executable package of software that includes everything needed to run an application: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries and settings (source and more info: www.docker.com)

- Postgres as database manager service, used to host the CMS database, for internal drupal functionality, and the PostGIS extended database containing the data used for DAP data, charts and maps;
- Pgadmin, a service providing a user interface to manage the database provided by the Postgres service;
- Drupal which provides the web server and drupal CMS for the DAP platform.
- Fastapi² application to serve interactive charts, powered by Plotly³ graphing library.
- Qgis-server⁴ implementing a full map server, fully integrated with QGIS Desktop application to create rich and dynamic maps

Finally, an additional management tool, namely Portainer⁵, has been introduced to manage the docker stack, have a synthetic view of the status of the platform component, access directly logs and terminals of each service in the stack.

Figura 11: Portainer web interface, for Docker stack management

² FastAPI is a modern, fast (high-performance), web framework for building APIs with Python. See more at <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

³ Interactive charts and maps for Python, R, Julia, Javascript, ggplot2, F#, MATLAB®, and Dash (<https://plotly.com/graphing-libraries/>)

⁴ QGIS Server is an open-source implementation of several standard web services (WMS, WFS, OGC API for Features 1.0 (WFS3) and WCS) that, in addition, implements advanced cartographic features for thematic mapping (more at https://docs.qgis.org/3.28/en/docs/server_manual/index.html)

⁵ Portainer hides the complexity of managing containers behind an easy-to-use User Interface and makes deploying apps and troubleshooting problems easier (see more at www.portainer.io)

3 DAP Demonstrator

DAP Demonstrator is hosted at Politecnico di Milano IT infrastructure and available at the following Url: <https://xake.deib.polimi.it:8080/dap> .

Platform content is currently populated with DAP outcomes described in Deliverable D4.4 “Robust portfolios planning and vulnerability analysis”.

Platform functionalities have been presented during three demonstrative sessions:

- on 19 September 2022, in the context of the International School On Water Reuse, held in Turin, with a set of demonstrative data;
- on 23 November 2022, when the methodology and the main results were presented and discussed at the headquarters of Acquedotto Pugliese in Bari in a final meeting entitled "Project Ô: Multi-objective analysis of the impacts of climate change in complex systems. The case demonstration of the Apulian Aqueduct" (see Deliverable D5.8 “DAP validation”).
- on 25 November 2022, in an online event where all Project Ô partners have been invited and DAP functionalities have been showcased.

Users attending the last two meetings received personal credentials to enter the platform, while all the other partners have been invited to apply for an account (at the following URL: <https://xake.deib.polimi.it:8080/dap/user/register>). An independent review of the final test session has been provided by Institute for Methods Innovation and described in the following Section 4.

At the delivery date of the present report, DAP has 20 registered users. The platform will be maintained and online for at least 6 months after the end of the Project and it will be used as a showcase of project outcomes.

Section 2.2 presented the stack of open-source software used to build the DAP: a mix of mature and well-known solutions with customized software components, packed together in a modern and modular architecture. This choice allowed the development team to reach two important goals, namely:

- re-use and extend the software developed for the User Collaborative Platform developed within WP7;
- create a portable and modular software solution, which has been exploited in two new projects, coherently with the goals of the Exploitation Plan, as described in Deliverable D9.5 (WP9).

Deliverable D4.2 has presented the software specially developed within WP4 activities for the implementation of DAP: now it has been released as open-source software, under the GNU General Public License v3⁶ and can be freely downloaded, used, and modified from the following repositories:

- Geoviz Drupal module: https://github.com/EILab-Polimi/prjo_dap_geoviz
- DAP Drupal module: https://github.com/EILab-Polimi/prjo_dap
- DAP Drupal theme: https://github.com/eilab-polimi/prjo_dap_theme
- DAP Docker Stack: https://github.com/eilab-polimi/prjo_dap_stack

⁶ See <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html> for more details.

4 DAP User Feedback Report

4.1 Introduction

The Institute for Methods Innovation was tasked with designing a user feedback questionnaire tailored to the DAP. The user testing questionnaire was designed to collect unmoderated feedback from remote testers. The survey focused on alignment between user expectations of the DAP and experiences with the interface, navigation, and explanations. For example, questions focused on ease of use and how intuitive the platform was for users.

4.2 Methods

Fondazione Politecnico invited partners within the Project Ô consortium to attend a live demonstration on 25 November 2022. This demonstration had 9 attendees, including 2 representatives from Institute for Methods Innovation and Fondazione Politecnico. To broaden the pool of testers after the demonstration, Fondazione Politecnico shared the materials and user testing survey with partners of the Project Ô consortium, who could not make it to the live demonstration. One reminder was sent 5 days after the invitation, and the survey was closed after 14 days.

The user feedback survey was started by 15 respondents from which 11 were fully completed, and 4 were partially completed. As a result, the number of responses per question depends on how far into the survey respondents progressed and whether the question was hidden through survey logic (e.g., further follow-up is unnecessary after an initial screening question). The survey design can be found in Appendix I.

4.3 Results: Overall

Demonstration Attendance

The first section screened respondents based on whether they had accessed the DAP. Most respondents indicated they had accessed the platform before completing the survey (Figure 12). This question was used to filter respondents before proceeding with more detailed questions about their experiences with the DAP.

Devices Used

Respondents were asked about the type of device and internet browsers used to access the platform used (Figures 12 and 14). The most common device used were laptops (n=4) and the platform was accessed mainly in Google Chrome (n=7) and Firefox (n=1). Other browsers were not used.

Figure 13: Devices used to access the platform

Figure 14: Internet browsers used to access the platform

DAP Functionalities Used

A question was posed to respondents about which DAP functionalities they used (Figure 15). There was an even distribution between the functionalities tested. All respondents of this question tried to “Browse different climate scenarios” (n=8). The second most used tried feature was “navigate water planning portfolios (WPP) through the outline” (n=7), followed by “evaluate each WPP impacts under different scenarios through interactive charts” and “use evaluation maps to verify the spatial distribution of impacts for different combinations of WPP and climate scenarios” (both n=6). Both features for “Compare different combinations of WPP and climate scenarios” and “add new indicators to WPP evaluation” were explored by just over half of the respondents (n=5).

Figure 15: Which of the following platform functions did you use?

Expected Gains from Platform Use

Users were asked what they expected to gain from using the platform (Table 1). Most responses focused on the application and future use of the technology by using it to better understand water demands and make impactful decisions on climate change mitigation actions.

Table 2: Open-ended questions on reasons using the platform

What are your reasons for using the platform?
Testing Project O tools and methods
testing project
Strengthening decision support tools*
To investigate Apulian water resources issues
I want to know more about ProjectO and the Apulian case study

4.4 Results: Demonstration feedback

The second section focused on the live demonstration on 25 November 2022 hosted by Fondazione Politecnico. These questions focused on whether respondents attended the live demonstration, when they used the platform in relation to the demonstration, and if they still had questions that needed to be answered after conclusion of the event (Table 3).

Table 3: Open-ended questions on expected gains

Questions			
Attend the live demonstration			
Use the platform during the live demonstration			
Use the platform after the live demonstration			
Have questions that still need to be answered	0	2	2

Overall, responses are almost evenly split between those who attended (n=6) and did not attend (n=5) the live demonstration. Respondents also indicated if they had used the platform during (n=1) and after (n=5) the demonstration, although it should be noted that most respondents only got personal access to the tool after the event. None of the respondents indicated still having questions that needed to be answered.

Time Spent on Platform Use

Additionally, users were also asked how much time they dedicated to exploring the platform following the demonstration (Figure 16). The durations reported for platform use included less than 30 minutes (n=1), 1-2 hours (n=2), 2-4 hours (n=1), and more than 4 hours (n=1).

Figure 16: After the demonstration, approximately how much time did you spend using the platform?

4.5 Results: User Perceptions & Experiences

The third and last section focused on user perceptions and experiences with the DAP and platform features. Indeed, all users (n=4) indicated that the platform and its features are useful to them now, as it stands. Additionally, none of the users (n=4) reported use of a similar platform in the past.

Overall Experience with Platform Use

Furthermore, users were asked to rate their overall experience with using the DAP and most users reported their experience as “neither difficult nor easy” (n=5). This is likely due to the platform offering complex features which require a high degree of background knowledge. Some users also might not have spent enough time on the platform to fully explore all features (see Figure 16). Over a third of all respondents to this question found the platform either “easy” (n=2) or “very easy” (n=1) to use.

Figure 17: How would you rate your overall experience with using the platform?

Ease of Platform Use

Afterwards, users were asked in more detail about specific aspects of the user experience with the DAP by being presented with statements, and an agreement scale from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree”. The first of these statements was whether “the platform was easy to use”. Most users either strongly agreed (n=3) or agreed (n=4) to this statement. Only two users felt neutral (n=1) or disagreed (n=1).

Figure 18: The platform was easy to use.

The reason provided by one user who disagreed was, “More guidance for the user is required. Maybe the needed information can be found in the deliverables, but time is needed to read them.” This user also felt the platform features were useful.

Ease of Finding Information on Platform

Most users agreed that they could “easily find what [they] were looking for on the platform” (n=5), or even strongly agreed (n=1). A third of respondents felt neutral about this statement (n=3).

Figure 19: I could easily find what I was looking for on the platform.

Clarity of Information on Platform

Most users agreed that information on the platform was clear (n=7). A third of respondents felt neutral about clarity of information (n=2).

Figure 20: Information on the platform was clear.

Comfort of Platform Use

Most users also agreed that the platform was comfortable to use (n=7). Only one user felt neutral about their comfort using the platform.

Figure 21: The platform was comfortable to use.

Interest in Platform Use for Work

Most users agreed about their “interest in using this platform for work”. A few users felt neutral (n=2) or disagreed (n=1).

Figure 22: I am interested in using this platform for my own work.

The reason provided by one user who disagreed was that they “don't need it for work now, maybe in the future”. This user also felt the platform features were useful but felt more user guidance was necessary.

Most Liked Aspects of Platform Use

Finally, users were asked what they like most and least about using the DAP (Tables 4 and 5). For most liked aspects, the capacity to work with complex data and compare different scenarios were mentioned. There was also mention of specific elements of the DAP, such as the “outline page” or “evaluation map”.

Table 4: Open ended responses to **most** liked aspects of using the platform

What did you like most about using this platform?

The easiness in comparing different scenarios' impacts and the high number of possible scenarios considered.

the ability to explore complex information

Exploring different solutions and scenarios to guide decision-making

Outline page, Evaluation Map

Least Liked Aspects of Platform Use

For the least liked aspects, one user noted that of “additional indicators could be more than those inserted”, which is helpful feedback for aligning platform features closer to real demands. Another user reported that they did not fully understand how to use the platform, but also highlights their absence during the workshop. This indicates that the complexity of the platform likely demands a sophisticated onboarding process to not overwhelm users with its features.

Table 5: Open ended responses to least liked aspects of using the platform

read.deliverables
nothing.to.dislike
clarify.functionality
Additional.indicators
implement.more.data
did.not.join.demo

What did you like least about using this platform?

Not understanding fully how to use it (but I didn't join the demo
neither read the deliverables)

Nothing to dislike, I'd just clarify the functionality and implement
more data.

Additional indicators could be more than those inserted.

4.6 Conclusion

Overall, feedback about the Decision Analytics Platform (DAP) functionality, usefulness and ease of use was largely positive and shows a viable proof of concept. Most users appreciated the toolset the DAP provides for working with complex data structures and quickly plotting scenarios. These conclusions are supported by the high level of agreement from users on the platform being useful as it currently stands. Most testers also felt enthusiastic about using the platform in their own work, except for those who do not typically work with such data.

While all users reported not having used a similar platform, the only confusion, concern, or technical difficulty presented was around the need for more user guidance to help clarify how the platform should be used. Findings show that some users may find the platform complex, which may lead to confusion and more difficult use. As such, there may be a need for additional indicators and guidance information, which could improve further iterations of the platform.

Finally, it is important to restate that our findings are based on a small sample of Project Ô stakeholders, including consortium partners and external consultants. Most consortium partners have been working with the ideas and concepts of the project while the external consultants were new to the ideas and concepts. Most of the negative feedback was provided by the external consultants with a great unfamiliarity. As such, we strongly recommend widening the platform demonstration to provide further opportunity for user testing with stakeholders outside of the Project Ô consortium. That is, there should be an additional round of testing with non-expert stakeholders completed prior to public launch. This further testing can help ensure the DAP will achieve its objectives with the desired stakeholders.

Appendix I – User Testing Feedback Questionnaire

Welcome!

Thank you for being willing to contribute your feedback about this platform. We are keen to understand your experiences and perspectives as a current and future platform user.

Here, you will find a number of questions about the user experience and your views about how useful the platform is for your work. Please be as honest and direct in your feedback as possible to help us improve the platform for users like you.

Participation in this research is voluntary. By default, your responses will be anonymised prior to reporting and publishing of data and results. No personally identifiable information will be shared with third parties for any reason without your explicit consent.

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Agreement to Participate

Please read the following statements below:

- I confirm I am 16 years of age or older.
- I understand that my responses to the following survey will be stored and used for research and evaluation purposes only.
- I understand the information I provide about myself is confidential.
- My identity will not be disclosed for commercial use by a third party or made public without my explicit consent.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I can withdraw at any time.
- I agree I have received adequate information about my participation in this survey and understand what will happen to the information I provide.

1.1. Please indicate whether you understand the information provided above, that you agree with the statements above, and that you are willing to participate in this survey: [Checkbox (Inline)]

Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey.

Shown if Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey. is NOT selected in 1.1. [Applies to text below]

If you would like clarification about any of the information above before starting, or if you have difficulties completing this form, please email support@methodsinnovation.org.

[PAGE BREAK]

2.1. Have you accessed the platform? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 2.1. [Applies to 2.2 to 2.6.]

2.2. What do you hope to gain from using the platform? [Text line]

2.3. What are your reasons for using the platform? [Text line]

2.4. Which type of device did you use? [Dropdown]

Desktop
Laptop

Tablet
Smartphone

Other (please specify)

2.5. Which browser did you use? [Dropdown]

Firefox
Google Chrome
Microsoft Edge

Opera
Brave
Internet Explorer

Unsure
Other (please specify)

2.6. Which of the following platform functions did you use? [Checkbox (Button)]

Navigated Water Planning Portfolios (WPP) through the Outline
Browsed different climate Scenarios
Evaluated each WPP impacts under different
Scenarios through interactive charts
Used evaluation maps to verify the spatial distribution of impacts for different combination
of WPP and climate Scenarios
Added new indicators to WPP evaluation
Compared different combinations of WPP and climate Scenarios

[PAGE BREAK]

3.1. Did you attend the live demonstration? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.1. [Applies to 3.2.]

3.2. Did you use the platform during the live demonstration? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.2. [Applies to 3.4.]

3.4. Were you able to ask questions? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.4. [Applies to 3.5.]

3.5. Were the answers you received helpful? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.2. [Applies to 3.6.]

3.6. Do you have questions that still need to be answered? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.1. [Applies to 3.3.]

3.3. Did you use the platform after the live demonstration? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

Shown if Yes selected in 3.3. [Applies to 3.7.]

3.7. After the demonstration, approximately how much time did you spend using the platform? [Likert Scale (5-point: Less than 30 minutes - More than 4 hours)]

[PAGE BREAK]

4.1. Is this platform useful to you now, as it currently stands? (i.e., if there are no changes) [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

4.2. Are the platform features useful? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

4.3. Have you ever used a platform similar to this in the past? [Likert Scale (3-point: Yes - No - Unsure)]

[PAGE BREAK]

5.1. How would you rate your overall experience with using the platform? [Likert Scale (5-point: Difficult - Easy)]

5.2. Please describe your experience with the platform: [Text line]

Using the response options below, please indicate your level of agreement: [Likert Scale (5-point: Agree - Disagree)] [5.3 to 5.7 in random order]

5.3. The platform was easy to use.

5.4. I could easily find what I was looking for on the platform.

5.5. Information on the platform was clear.

5.6. The platform was comfortable to use.

5.7. I am interested in using this platform for my own work.

5.8. What did you like the most about using this platform? [Text line]

5.9. What did you like least about using this platform? [Text line]